

LEADERSHIP AND CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE: PAST, PRESENT, FUTURE

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Abstract

Cultural intelligence has become crucial in organizational leadership due to increasingly intercultural business and work environments. This paper aims to advance the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence by revealing its past, present, and future. Science mapping of the intellectual and conceptual structure of the field was conducted using three bibliometric techniques: co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis. Based on articles from the Web of Science database published from 2003 to 2023, we provided a systematic and focused bibliometric review of research on leadership and cultural intelligence in the last two decades. The findings indicate that the past of the research field has been connected with the theoretical foundations and empirical evidence on the influence of cultural intelligence on leader performance and effectiveness in intercultural settings. The present is focused on the role of cultural intelligence in transformational leadership and team leadership in global, virtual and culturally diverse environments. The future of the research field could be directed toward addressing the identified knowledge gaps related to inclusive leadership, employee well-being, engagement and retention, and organizational cultural intelligence. The ultimate purpose of advancing the research field is to inspire the development and demonstration of cultural intelligence in leadership practice.

Keywords: Leadership, Cultural Intelligence, Intercultural Environment, Bibliometric Analysis, Review

1 INTRODUCTION

Business and work environments are becoming increasingly intercultural. Leadership as “the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done [...] to accomplish shared objectives” (Yukl, 2006, p. 8) is more complex and challenging in such environments. Leaders need to continuously adapt and interact with employees, business partners and other stakeholders whose values, norms and behaviors may differ significantly. Cultural intelligence as the capability to function effectively in intercultural contexts (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008; Early & Ang, 2003) has become crucial in organizational leadership.

Interculturality within organizations is expected to grow due to further workforce migration and demands for greater diversity, equity, and inclusion. In recent decades, the share of interna-

tional migrants in the world population has increased (McAuliffe & Triandafyllidou, 2021). This trend could intensify due to diverging demographic trends and economic disparities (The World Bank, 2023). The growing cultural diversity of the workforce imposes a need for inclusive leadership. Such leadership recognizes differences among people as a source of strength and advancement, both on the individual and organizational levels (Hays-Thomas, 2022). It implies building an organizational culture where all individuals feel accepted, valued and rewarded, regardless of their cultural backgrounds (Garg & Sangwan, 2021). Fostering diversity, equity, and inclusion requires leaders’ awareness, knowledge, motivation, and behaviors that contribute to the well-being and effectiveness of employees from different cultures, all of which are components of cultural intelligence (Van Dyne et al., 2012).

Cultural intelligence in leadership is therefore expected to be even more relevant in the future. Although the construct of cultural intelligence has attracted increasing attention from leadership researchers in recent years, their primary focus has been on emotional intelligence (Pitsi et al., 2023). The existing bibliometric reviews of the field are related to research on cultural intelligence and specific leadership constructs, such as multinational, multicultural, and school leadership (Anathuri et al., 2022; Bratianu & Paiuc, 2022; Paiuc, 2021a). They combine performance analysis and science mapping that differ in their purpose. Our review encompasses research on cultural intelligence and all leadership constructs and focuses exclusively on science mapping of the field. Additionally, it refers to the period from 2003, when Early and Ang introduced the construct of cultural intelligence, to the end of 2023, thus presenting a systematic overview of the leadership and cultural intelligence literature in the last two decades.

This paper aims to advance the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence, with the ultimate purpose of inspiring the development and demonstration of cultural intelligence in leadership practice to improve the well-being and effectiveness of individuals and organizations operating in intercultural environments. We attempt to answer the following research question: What is the past, present, and future of the research field? For this purpose, science mapping of the intellectual and conceptual structure of the field was conducted using three bibliometric techniques: co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis. The triangulation of these techniques enables a snapshot of the past, present, and future of the research field (Lamovšek & Černe, 2023) by uncovering foundational, periodical, and key themes (Donthu et al., 2021).

The introductory part of the paper is followed by a literature review. To broaden the understanding of the relevance of cultural intelligence in leadership, we first briefly describe the related constructs of intelligence and culture in general in connection with leadership. The methods and results are then presented, followed by a discussion that includes practical implications, limitations, and further research recommendations. Finally, the conclusion highlights the study's key contributions.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Intelligence and leadership

Intelligence is considered essential to the emergence and effectiveness of leadership (Antonakis et al., 2019). The definitions of intelligence proposed by organizations, psychologists, and researchers in artificial intelligence are predominantly referring to one's capability, ability, or capacity to understand, learn, and adapt (Legg & Hutter, 2007). According to the traditional approach based on Binet's scale and Spearman's theory of general intelligence, this psychological construct refers only to one's cognitive ability to solve certain problems (Davis et al., 2011), without the consideration of contextual and situational factors. The contemporary approaches are addressing this limitation by identifying multiple dimensions of intelligence and taking environmental factors into account. Sternberg (1986) proposed four major loci of intelligence: biological loci (structural and process aspects, and the interaction between them); cognitive loci (ordinary cognition and metacognition); motivational loci (the intensity and direction of cognitions); and behavioral loci (actions as a function of cognitive processes). This multilocus framework provided the theoretical foundation for the conceptualization and empirical validation of the construct of cultural intelligence (Ang et al., 2015a).

While a certain level of general intelligence can be considered a foundation for the effectiveness of leadership (Antonakis et al., 2019), research on the role of intelligence in leadership indicated the need for a broader conceptualization of intelligence (Ang et al., 2015a; Davis et al., 2011; Riggio et al., 2002). Riggio et al. (2002) mention that constructs such as "emotional maturity", "social skills and insight", and "tact" were all related to leadership effectiveness by early researchers, and they are all closely related to the different types of intelligence that are relevant in contemporary leadership research. These specific intelligence constructs that connect intelligence with the adaptation to social, emotional and intercultural environments are social intelligence (Thorndike & Stein, 1937), emotional intelligence (Mayer & Salovey, 1993; Salovey & Mayer, 1990), and cultural intelligence (Ang & Van Dyne, 2008; Earley & Ang, 2003). A combination of multiple forms of intelligence can "make leaders effective in a range of lead-

ership situations because they involve abilities to adapt to a variety of social and interpersonal situations” (Riggio et al., 2002, p. 3). Multiple intelligences are thus of particular importance to leading teams and organizations in continuously changing and culturally diverse environments.

2.2 Culture and leadership

Differences in culture can influence the conception, enactment, and development of leadership (Koopman et al., 1999; Lumby & Foskett, 2009). Culture should also be considered in the conceptualization of intelligence; “otherwise the concept is lacking some utility” (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015, p. xiii). A variety of learnt behaviors and practices are referred to as culture, “regardless whether people engage in them consciously or unconsciously” (Kemmelmeier & Kusano, 2018, p. 622). According to Hofstede, “culture is the collective programming of the mind with three software levels that operate in every person: human nature, culture, and personality” (Paiuc, 2021b, p. 83). This programming of the mind happens through “life experiences, symbols, heroes, rituals and values” (Eken et al., 2014, p. 157). Culture is dynamic (Livermore, 2009) and collective (Eken et al., 2014). Trompenaars and Hampden-Turner (2011) distinguished between corporate culture and national culture, while culture itself can make distinctions between nations, occupations, and organizations (Eken et al., 2014).

Accomplishing cross-cultural and intercultural effectiveness of leadership requires more than a knowledge of different cultures (Deng & Gibson, 2008). Although cultural dimensions such as individualism/collectivism and uncertainty avoidance (Hofstede, 2011) can explain preferences that distinguish countries, they are not taking into account the uniqueness of individuals and the fact that “cultures do not equate with nations” (Paiuc, 2021b, p. 83). In addition, the global interconnectedness is impacting individuals’ values, norms and behaviors making them more similar across countries that were traditionally considered culturally distinct. Leadership assessment and development programs are largely similar around the world (Lumby & Foskett, 2009). Considering that business and work environments are becoming increasingly intercultural, leaders need to have universally relevant capabilities to under-

stand, learn from, and foster the inclusion of individuals from many different cultures. Therefore, the cultural dimension approach does not adequately meet the needs of organizational leadership in intercultural environments. The construct that contributes to addressing that problem is cultural intelligence.

2.3 Cultural intelligence and leadership

The utility of the cultural intelligence (CQ) construct introduced by Earley and Ang (2003) has been demonstrated in leadership research. According to Ang et al. (2015a), cultural intelligence is distinct from other perspectives on intelligence and culture. One of the most important distinctions they emphasize is that cultural intelligence enables effectiveness across different intercultural environments, and not just in a specific culture. Therefore, cultural intelligence integrates the capabilities that are universally applicable and useful across cultures. In this sense, “cultural intelligence is culture-free” (Ang et al., 2015b, p. 433). In the intelligence literature, cultural intelligence is conceptually positioned “as a set of abilities or capabilities, as opposed to personality or interests” (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015, p. 8). Van Dyne et al. (2012) explained cultural intelligence as “an individual’s capability to detect, assimilate, reason, and act on cultural cues appropriately in situations characterized by cultural diversity” (p. 297). These situations can appear in different intercultural contexts, including national, organizational, and other cultures.

Individual cultural intelligence reflects the contemporary approach to viewing intelligence as a multifactor capability by encompassing metacognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral dimensions (Ang & Van Dyne, 2015; Ang & Van Dyne, 2008; Ang et al., 2007; Van Dyne et al., 2010). These dimensions also served as a basis for the development of a Cultural Intelligence Scale (CQS) in the form of a self-report (Ang et al., 2007) and observer report (Van Dyne et al., 2008). Metacognitive CQ refers to one’s awareness before and during interactions with people from different cultures and relates to planning approaches, observing thoughts, questioning assumptions, reflecting on reactions, and adjusting attitudes. Cognitive CQ is the general cultural knowledge and knowledge of cultural differences related to social, economic, legal, educational, and other sys-

tems. Motivational CQ is the capability based on intrinsic and/or extrinsic interest and self-efficacy related to the drive to learn about different cultures and function effectively in intercultural situations and settings. Behavioral CQ refers to the capability to demonstrate appropriate both verbal and nonverbal behaviors in intercultural environments by adjusting to the cultural specifics of each encounter.

Organizational cultural intelligence was conceptualized by identifying its managerial, competitive, and structural aspects (Ang & Inkpen, 2008). The levels of cultural intelligence of individual members of the senior management team are combined in managerial CQ. The extent to which organizations have processes and practices for international knowledge integration is referred to as competitive CQ. The organization's capability to plan and build effective routines for relationships with international business partners refers to structural CQ. Based on this conceptualization, Lima et al. (2016) developed a scale for measuring organizational CQ that consists of five factors: leadership behavior, adaptability, intentionality, training, and inclusion. Livermore et al. (2022) suggested that organizational CQ can be developed by integrating it into an organization's mission, adapting routines to align with the diversity in cultural values across the organization, and fostering inclusion through organizational practices related to hiring and promotion, information sharing, decision making, and learning and development.

To understand the specifics of cultural intelligence that are relevant to leadership research, it is crucial to clarify its distinctiveness in connection with social and emotional intelligence. The construct of "cultural intelligence is a subset of social intelligence, as cultural intelligence skills are variants of social intelligence" (Crowne, 2009, p. 155). In other words, cultural intelligence requires social intelligence. However, individuals who have high social intelligence in one cultural environment, such as a country, organization, or professional group, do not necessarily behave in a socially intelligent manner in other cultural or intercultural environments. Cultural intelligence can be therefore considered an upgrade of social intelligence. Furthermore, although cultural intelligence and emotional intelligence partially overlap in terms of awareness of

one's own and others' emotions, these constructs are distinct because individuals who are highly emotionally intelligent in their domestic cultural setting may not be as emotionally intelligent when interacting with people from different cultures (Crowne, 2009; Earley & Peterson, 2004). Thus, the construct of cultural intelligence is of particular importance to leadership research in intercultural contexts.

3 METHODS

Bibliometric methods refer to a quantitative approach to reviewing published research but they are employed to draw conclusions concerning qualitative aspects (Wallin, 2005). Bibliometric analysis allows researchers to advance a research field by providing a systematic, objective and reproducible overview of the literature that can contribute to both theory development and practice improvement (Mukherjee et al., 2022). This method is increasingly used by researchers across scientific fields due to the potential to produce high research impact as well as the availability and advancement of online scientific databases and bibliometric software (Donthu et al., 2021).

The two main categories of bibliometric analysis techniques are performance analysis and science mapping. Performance analysis examines the impact and productivity based on the contributions of research constituents (e.g., authors, journals, and countries), while science mapping uncovers knowledge clusters in the research field based on the relationships between research constituents (Donthu et al., 2021; Lamovšek & Černe, 2023). To answer the research question in this study, we conducted a bibliometric analysis using a science mapping technique that can offer insight into the structure of the research field. The intellectual structure indicates the most influential authors, publications, or journals, whereas the conceptual structure reveals the main themes and patterns of the research field (Khare & Jain, 2022).

Science mapping was conducted by employing three bibliometric techniques: co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis. Co-citation analysis uses the frequency with which two units are cited together "to construct measures of similarity between documents, authors or journals"

(Zupic & Cater, 2015, p. 3). It derives thematic clusters based on cited publications and uncovers seminal publications that represent the knowledge foundation and the past of the research field (Donthu et al., 2021). Bibliographic coupling “uses the number of references shared by two documents as a measure of the similarity between them” (Zupic & Cater, 2015, p. 5). Since the thematic clusters are based on the citing publications, when the analysis includes documents published in the recent period it is connected to the present of the field (Donthu et al., 2021). Co-word analysis “uses the words in documents to establish relationships and build a conceptual structure of the domain” (Zupic & Cater, 2015, p. 6). It can contribute to forecasting the future of the research field by uncovering the key themes and identifying knowledge gaps (Donthu et al., 2021).

A bibliometric analysis protocol encompassed the selection of a digital database, search strategy, and inclusion criteria. The search was conducted in the Web of Science Core Collection (WoS) database on January 21, 2024. The searched terms were “leadership” AND “cultural intelligence” included in the title, abstract, and/or keywords. The search was limited to the period 2003-2023 to present a systematic overview of the literature on leadership and cultural intelligence in the last two decades. It included all research fields and journal articles in English only. The total number of articles found amounted to 333. Since the search resulted in articles also related to research on leadership concerning organizational and other cultures, we refined the search by including in the criteria that keywords must include “leadership” and “cultural intelligence”. The final number of articles found and included in the bibliometric analysis amounted to 163. Most articles were from the fields of management (74), business (32), and education research (22).

VOSviewer software (version 1.6.18) developed by Van Eck and Waltman (2010) was used to conduct the bibliometric analysis and create a network visualization based on the data obtained from WoS. VOSviewer constructs and displays distance-based bibliometric networks “in which the distance between two items reflects the strength of the relation between the items” (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010, p. 525). This allows for identifying the clusters of related items represented by different colors (Van Eck & Waltman, 2010).

4 RESULTS

4.1 Co-citation analysis

The unit of analysis was cited references and the minimum number of citations of a cited reference was set to 20. The full counting method was applied. Of the 9,619 cited references, 26 items met the threshold. The total strength of the co-citation links with other cited references was calculated for each of the 26 items. Table 1 shows the top 10 most influential works (cited publications) according to the total link strength based on co-citation analysis.

Figure 1 illustrates the co-citation network consisting of three clusters: Conceptualization and measurement of cultural intelligence, Nomological network of cultural intelligence, and Sub(dimensions) of cultural intelligence.

Cluster 1: Conceptualization and measurement of cultural intelligence. Cluster 1 marked in red includes 12 items. The most influential publications are the seminal works of Earley and Ang (2003) and Ang et al. (2007) which represent the knowledge foundation of the research field considering that they conceptualize the construct of cultural intelligence and develop the Cultural Intelligence Scale for its measurement in the form of self-report. This cluster also includes publications of Earley (2002) and Earley and Mosakowski (2004) that indicated the importance of intercultural understanding and contributed to the establishment of the construct of cultural intelligence. Several publications in this cluster discuss the effects of cultural intelligence on cross-border leadership effectiveness (Rockstuhl et al., 2011), innovation (Elenkov & Manev, 2009), offshore outsourcing success (Ang & Inkpen, 2008), and global leadership success (Alon & Higgins, 2005).

Cluster 2: Nomological network of cultural intelligence. Cluster 2 marked in green includes 7 items. The key cited publication in this cluster is *Handbook of cultural intelligence: Theory, measurement, and applications* edited by Ang and Van Dyne (2008) which introduces the Cultural Intelligence Scale in the observer form (Van Dyne et al., 2008). It also extends the nomological network of cultural intelligence by identifying its antecedents, other correlates (general, social, emotional, and practical intelligence), intervening constructs, situational fac-

Table 1: Most influential works based on co-citation analysis

Author(s) / Year	Title	Cit.	TLS
Ang et al. (2007)	“Cultural intelligence: Its measurement and effects on cultural judgment and decision making, cultural adaptation and task performance”	104	695
Earley & Ang (2003)	“Cultural intelligence: Individual interactions across cultures”	110	678
Ang & Van Dyne (2008)	“Handbook of cultural intelligence: Theory, measurement, and applications”	45	362
Van Dyne et al. (2012)	“Sub-dimensions of the four factor model of cultural intelligence: Expanding the conceptualization and measurement of cultural intelligence”	43	341
Ang et al. (2006)	“Personality correlates of the four-factor model of cultural intelligence”	49	339
Rockstuhl et al. (2011)	“Beyond general intelligence (IQ) and emotional intelligence (EQ): The role of cultural intelligence (CQ) on cross-border leadership effectiveness in a globalized world”	44	334
Imai & Gelfand (2010)	“The culturally intelligent negotiator: The impact of cultural intelligence (CQ) on negotiation sequences and outcomes”	32	283
Elenkov & Manev (2009)	“Senior expatriate leadership’s effects on innovation and the role of cultural intelligence”	29	272
Templer et al. (2006)	“Motivational cultural intelligence, realistic job preview, realistic living conditions preview, and cross-cultural adjustment”	34	270
Groves & Feyerherm (2011)	“Leader cultural intelligence in context: Testing the moderating effects of team cultural diversity on leader and team performance”	35	269

Notes: Cit. – citations; TLS – total link strength

Figure 1: Co-citation network

tors, and individual and interpersonal outcomes. Other publications in this cluster are focused on the outcomes of cultural intelligence related to interpersonal trust (Rockstuhl & Ng, 2008), negotiation (Imai & Gelfand, 2010), general, work and interaction cross-cultural adjustment (Templer et al., 2006), team performance and leader performance (Groves & Feyerherm, 2011).

Cluster 3: Sub(dimensions) of cultural intelligence. Cluster 3 marked in blue includes 7 items. The most influential publication in this cluster is of Van Dyne et al. (2012) which deepens the understanding of metacognitive, cognitive, motivational and behavioral dimensions of cultural intelligence by conceptualizing their sub-dimensions. This cluster also includes publications that provided a review of previous conceptual and empirical studies of cultural intelligence (Ng et al., 2012), explained behaviors that are considered intelligent in culturally diverse environments (Brislin et al., 2006), and offered insight into how certain types and level of exposure to other cultures result in increased cultural intelligence (Crowne, 2008).

The conceptual study by Triandis (2006) included in this cluster described various aspects of cultural intelligence in an organizational context.

4.2 Bibliographic coupling

The unit of analysis was documents and the minimum number of citations of a document was set to 15. The full counting method was applied. Of the 163 documents, 50 items met the threshold for which the total strength of the bibliographic coupling links with other documents was calculated. Table 2 shows the top 10 most influential works (citing publications) according to the total link strength based on bibliographic coupling.

The bibliographic coupling network consists of four clusters: Leadership development and effectiveness in global, international and culturally diverse environments, Adaptive, empowering and transformational leadership approaches, Cross-cultural adaptation, performance and transformational leadership, and Global, virtual and multicultural teams (Figure 2).

Table 2: Most influential works based on bibliographic coupling

Author(s) / Year	Title	Cit.	TLS
Jyoti & Kour (2017a)	"Factors affecting cultural intelligence and its impact on job performance: Role of cross-cultural adjustment, experience and perceived social support"	43	475
Setti et al. (2022)	"Enhancing expatriates' assignments success: the relationships between cultural intelligence, cross-cultural adaptation and performance"	32	428
Aldhaheri (2017)	"Cultural intelligence and leadership style in the education sector"	18	389
Azevedo & Shane (2019)	"A new training program in developing cultural intelligence can also improve innovative work behavior and resilience: A longitudinal pilot study of graduate students and professional employees"	32	361
Jyoti & Kour (2017b)	"Cultural intelligence and job performance: An empirical investigation of moderating and mediating variables"	21	359
Ramsey et al. (2017)	"Developing global transformational leaders"	31	357
Erez et al. (2013)	"Going global: Developing management students' cultural intelligence and global identity in culturally diverse virtual teams"	150	342
Ng et al. (2009)	"From experience to experiential learning: Cultural intelligence as a learning capability for global leader development"	288	337
Van Dyne et al. (2012)	"Sub-dimensions of the four factor model of cultural intelligence: Expanding the conceptualization and measurement of cultural intelligence"	217	336
Ramsey et al. (2016)	"Emergence of cultural intelligence and global mindset capital: a multilevel model"	16	323

Notes: Cit. – citations; TLS – total link strength

Figure 2: Bibliographic coupling network

Cluster 1: Leadership development and effectiveness in global, international and culturally diverse environments. Cluster 1 marked in red includes 18 items. The most influential citing publication is of Ng et al. (2009) which examined the moderating role of cultural intelligence in the relationship between international work assignments and outcomes relevant to global leadership development. This cluster also includes the previously mentioned most influential cited studies that introduced the conceptualization of the sub-dimensions of cultural intelligence (Van Dyne et al., 2012) and showed that cultural intelligence is a more significant predictor of leader cross-border effectiveness than general and emotional intelligence (Rockstuhl et al., 2011). Other publications in this cluster indicated that cultural intelligence is positively related to international leadership potential (Kim & Van Dyne, 2012), transformational leadership (Keung & Rockinson-Szapkiw, 2013), and leaders' knowledge sharing (Chen & Lin, 2013) and performance (Groves & Feyerherm, 2011) in culturally diverse teams.

Cluster 2: Adaptive, empowering and transformational leadership approaches. Cluster 2 marked in green includes 16 items. The publications in this

cluster showed that cultural intelligence contributes to the school leaders' capability to adapt their leadership approaches within a culturally diverse environment (Aldhaheri, 2017) and is positively related to empowering leadership (Solomon & Steyn, 2017), while transformational leadership was found to be a mediator in the relationship between cultural intelligence and employee voice behavior (Afsar et al., 2019). This cluster also includes the publications that confirmed the positive effects of leader cultural intelligence on perceived supervisor support (Guang & Charoensukmongkol, 2022) and pro-diversity climate (Charoensukmongkol & Phungsoonthorn, 2022). Several other studies in this cluster indicate a positive relationship between cultural intelligence of students and employees on their innovative behavior, mediated by interpersonal trust and work engagement (Afsar et al., 2021; Azevedo & Shane, 2019; Kistyanto et al., 2022).

Cluster 3: Cross-cultural adaptation, performance and transformational leadership. Cluster 3 marked in blue includes 9 items. The publications in this cluster indicated that cultural intelligence is positively related to leader job performance (Jyoti & Kour, 2017a, 2017b), expatriate contextual/manage-

rial performance (Setti et al., 2022), firms' innovation performance (Berraies, 2020), and employees' job performance (Nam & Park, 2019). The relationship between cultural intelligence and performance was found to be mediated by cross-cultural adaptation (Jyoti & Kour, 2017a, 2017b; Setti et al., 2022) and knowledge sharing (Berraies, 2020). This cluster also reveals the interconnectedness of cultural intelligence and transformational leadership. Research confirmed that cultural intelligence was a significant predictor of transformational leadership (Nam & Park, 2019; Ramsey et al., 2017) and a moderator in the relationship between transformational leadership and expatriate adjustment and performance (Lee et al., 2013).

Cluster 4: Global, virtual and multicultural teams. Cluster 4 marked in yellow includes 7 items. The most influential publications in this cluster examined the impact of cultural training in the form of a virtual multicultural team project. They revealed that such training increased cultural intelligence and global identity of students (Erez et al., 2013) and improved global team members' cultural intelligence which, in turn, positively influenced individual-level task performance (Presbitero & Toledano, 2018), as well as that individuals with high cultural intelligence were considerably more likely to emerge as leaders in culturally diverse teams (Lisak & Erez, 2015). In addition, the team leader's cultural intelligence was found to be a moderator in the relationship between perceived cultural dissimilarity and team member's cultural intelligence (Presbitero, 2020).

4.3 Co-word analysis

The unit of analysis was author keywords and the minimum number of occurrences of a keyword was set to 3. The full counting method was applied. Of the 465 keywords, 27 met the threshold for which the total strength of the co-occurrence links with other keywords was calculated. The keywords "quantitative" and "uae" were removed before forming the co-word network since they were not relevant to uncovering the key research themes. Table 3 includes a list of the top 15 most frequent keywords according to the total link strength based on co-word analysis.

Table 3: Most frequent keywords based on co-word analysis

Keyword	Occur.	TLS
cultural intelligence	82	92
leadership	19	26
emotional intelligence	12	17
global leadership	10	14
expatriates	7	12
multicultural teams	6	11
trust	6	11
diversity	7	10
transformational leadership	7	10
CQ	4	8
cross-cultural management	5	8
social intelligence	4	8
team performance	4	8
global virtual teams	4	7
global mindset	7	6

Notes: Occur. – occurrences; TLS – total link strength

Figure 3 illustrates the co-word network consisting of three clusters: Multiple intelligences and culturally diverse teams, Global and transformational leadership, and Leadership in cross-cultural contexts.

Cluster 1: Multiple intelligences and culturally diverse teams. Cluster 1 marked in red includes 12 keywords: "emotional intelligence", "multicultural teams", "trust", "social intelligence", "team performance", "global virtual teams", "creativity", "innovative behavior", "interpersonal trust", "knowledge sharing", "performance", and "cultural diversity".

Cluster 2: Global and transformational leadership. Cluster 2 marked in green includes 7 keywords: "cultural intelligence", "global leadership", "transformational leadership", "CQ", "global mindset", "international experience", and "self-efficacy".

Cluster 3: Leadership in cross-cultural contexts. Cluster 3 marked in blue includes 6 keywords: "leadership", "expatriates", "diversity", "cross-cultural management", "multinational enterprises", and "culture".

Figure 3: Co-word network

5 DISCUSSION

We presented a bibliometric review of research on cultural intelligence and all leadership constructs published from 2003 to 2023. A search in the Web of Science database resulted in only 163 articles that included both “leadership” and “cultural intelligence” as keywords, which indicates that this research field is still in its development phase. Therefore, revealing its past and present and, in particular, identifying the potential directions of its development in the future can contribute to the advancement of the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence. Mapping of the intellectual structure was based on the most influential cited and citing publications. The analysis of the content of these publications and author keywords enabled the mapping of the conceptual structure that uncovered fundamental, periodical, and key themes relevant to capturing the past, present, and future of the field.

Past of the research field. The co-citation analysis showed that the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence started by gaining an understanding

of the construct of cultural intelligence and its potential applications in leadership research. Considering that a significant body of knowledge on leadership already existed, leadership researchers focused their literature reviews on cultural intelligence. The most influential cited publications in the last two decades are the works of Earley and Ang (2003), Ang et al. (2007), Ang and Van Dyne (2008), and Van Dyne et al. (2012), which introduce or extend the conceptualization, measurement and nomological network of cultural intelligence. Early empirical research in the field that is most influential and relevant to understanding the specific effects of cultural intelligence on leadership outcomes indicated that cultural intelligence is positively related to leader cross-border effectiveness (Rockstuhl et al., 2011) and leader performance in culturally diverse teams (Groves & Feyerherm, 2011). The past of the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence has therefore been connected with the theoretical foundations of cultural intelligence and empirical evidence on the influence of cultural intelligence on leader performance and effectiveness in intercultural settings.

Present of the research field. Bibliographic coupling indicated that the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence continued to examine the impact of cultural intelligence on leadership performance and effectiveness in global, international and culturally diverse environments. Since Cluster 2 (Adaptive, empowering and transformational leadership approaches) encompasses research published in the period from 2016 to 2023, it most closely reflects the present of the research field. The researchers' focus on these themes is understandable due to the growing need to adapt leadership approaches in constantly changing environments and to empower employees in such environments through individualized consideration regardless of cultural differences, and all of this can be considered an integral part of transformational leadership (Bass, 1985; Bass & Riggio, 2006). The most influential citing publications included in three out of four clusters examined the interconnectedness of cultural intelligence and transformational leadership (Afsar et al., 2019; Keung & Rockinson-Szapkiw, 2013; Lee et al., 2013; Nam & Park, 2019; Ramsey et al., 2017). Another important current stream of research indicates that being part of global, virtual, and multicultural teams develops cultural intelligence and that cultural intelligence contributes to the emergence and performance of leadership in such teams. Thus, it can be concluded that the present of the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence is focused on the role of cultural intelligence in transformational leadership and team leadership in global, virtual and culturally diverse environments.

Future of the research field. The co-word analysis showed that the key themes of research on leadership and cultural intelligence were global and transformational leadership, multicultural and global virtual teams and their performance, and emotional and social intelligence. These findings suggest that the research field in the past two decades has focused only on two broadly conceptualized leadership constructs but not specifically on inclusive leadership which is of key importance in increasingly diverse work environments. In addition, an emphasis was on team- and leader-level performance, while employee-level outcomes have been under-researched. The

consideration of emotional and social intelligence in research on the relationship between cultural intelligence and leadership was needed to advance the understanding of their interconnectedness and distinctiveness. Although the concept of organizational cultural intelligence was introduced in the literature, the co-word analysis showed that it was not one of the key research themes. The future of the research field of leadership and cultural intelligence could be directed toward addressing the identified knowledge gaps related to inclusive leadership, employee well-being, engagement and retention, and organizational cultural intelligence.

5.1 Future research recommendations

On the basis of the identified knowledge gaps in the field of leadership and cultural intelligence and the contemporary demands of employees and other stakeholders toward organizational leadership in intercultural environments, we suggest three key thematic areas on which future research could be directed.

First, inclusive leadership is needed to leverage cultural diversity within work environments for individual and organizational advancement. Although already researched constructs of transformational and empowering leadership may involve fostering inclusion to accomplish shared objectives, inclusive leadership additionally facilitates belongingness, ensures justice and equity, promotes diverse contributions, and highlights the value of the uniqueness of individuals (Randel et al., 2018). Thus, future research could focus on examining the role of leader cultural intelligence in inclusive leadership, both as a predictor and moderator of the relationship between inclusive leadership and outcomes on the leader, employee, and organizational levels.

Second, employee well-being, engagement and retention are of increasing importance for effective human resource management. We therefore suggest that future studies conducted in intercultural contexts explore the influence of leader cultural intelligence on these employee-level outcomes. In addition, employee well-being, engagement and

retention could also be examined as mediators in the relationship between leader cultural intelligence and effectiveness on the level of a leader, team, and organization. In this way, future research could contribute to understanding not only to what extent cultural intelligence can be positively related to intercultural effectiveness but also why and how such an effect occurs.

Third, organizational cultural intelligence could become one of the significant factors in the effectiveness of organizations and their leadership. Future qualitative studies could explore the perceptions of both leaders and employees regarding leadership values and behaviors that contribute to initiating and implementing practices that reflect organizational cultural intelligence, such as building and nurturing relationships with international business partners, integrating cultural knowledge, and fostering an inclusive work environment (Ang & Inkpen, 2008; Livermore et al., 2022). Quantitative research could focus on examining the influence of organizational cultural intelligence on leadership and organizational effectiveness, as well as on employee well-being.

5.2 Practical implications

Even though the primary purpose of this study was to provide a basis for researchers to further advance the field of leadership and cultural intelligence, it offers insights that are also useful for various practitioners. The results of the bibliometric review could raise awareness of leaders, human resources managers, and leadership development specialists operating in intercultural business and work environments on the influence of individual cultural intelligence on outcomes on the level of a leader, team, and organization. Organizational leadership at all levels could improve their performance and effectiveness in culturally diverse settings by developing and demonstrating meta-cognitive, cognitive, motivational, and behavioral cultural intelligence. Human resources managers could incorporate the assessment of cultural intelligence into the leadership recruitment processes, as well as in leadership selection to identify candidates among current employees for leadership succession and development. Lead-

ership development specialists could use the findings of this study as a rationale for obtaining support from organizational leadership and human resources managers when proposing tailored leadership development programs that include the development of cultural intelligence.

5.3 Limitations

The main limitation of this study is that the bibliometric review is based exclusively on articles from the Web of Science Core Collection database. Although the consolidation of different bibliometric data formats increases the possibility of human errors, the inclusion of articles from other databases could have affected the results of bibliometric analyses, especially of the co-word analysis. Therefore, the generalizability of the conclusions regarding knowledge gaps in research on leadership and cultural intelligence is undermined.

6 CONCLUSION

This study contributes to the leadership and cultural intelligence literature by providing a systematic and focused bibliometric review of research in the last two decades. By mapping the intellectual and conceptual structure using multiple bibliometric techniques, we offered insights into the past and present of the research field and provided ideas in which direction it could develop in the future. The qualitative literature review on the constructs of intelligence, culture, and cultural intelligence in connection with leadership complements the bibliometric review based on quantitative indicators, therefore this study allows both researchers and practitioners to broaden their understanding of the relevance of cultural intelligence in leadership. The ultimate purpose of advancing the research field is inspiring the development and demonstration of cultural intelligence in leadership practice to improve the well-being and effectiveness of individuals and organizations operating in intercultural environments.

EXTENDED SUMMARY/IZVLEČEK

Kulturna inteligentnost je postala ključnega pomena v organizacijskem vodenju zaradi vse bolj medkulturnega poslovnega in delovnega okolja. Namen prispevka je prispevati k razvoju raziskovalnega področja vodenja in kulturne inteligentnosti s prikazom njegove preteklosti, sedanjosti in prihodnosti. Mapiranje znanstvenega področja glede njegove intelektualne in konceptualne strukture je bilo izvedeno z uporabo treh bibliometričnih tehnik: analize so-citiranja, bibliografske povezanosti in analize skupnega pojavljanja besed. Na podlagi člankov iz podatkovne zbirke Web of Science, objavljenih med letoma 2003 in 2023, smo pripravili sistematičen in ciljno usmerjen bibliometrični pregled raziskav o vodenju in kulturni inteligentnosti v zadnjih dveh desetletjih. Ugotovitve kažejo, da je bila preteklost raziskovalnega področja povezana s teoretičnimi temelji in empiričnimi dokazi o vplivu kulturne inteligentnosti na uspešnost in učinkovitost vodij v medkulturnih kontekstih. Trenutno raziskovanje se osredotoča na vlogo kulturne inteligentnosti v transformacijskem in timskem vodenju v globalnem, virtualnem in kulturno raznolikem okolju. Prihodnji razvoj raziskovalnega področja bi se lahko usmeril v naslavljanje ugotovljenih vrzeli v znanju, povezanih z vključujočim vodenjem, blaginjo zaposlenih, zavzetostjo in zadržanjem kadrov ter organizacijsko kulturno inteligentnostjo. Končni namen nadaljnjega razvoja področja je spodbuditi krepitev in udejanjanje kulturne inteligentnosti v praksi vodenja.

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